

More of the same or a significant step forward in data-based cycling research and promotion?!

CRBAM 2025 Amsterdam Workshop Summary

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The end of the scientific method?

It's 17 years since the editor in chief of Wired Magazine published his provocative piece on the end of the scientific method and the new era of data-driven everything [1]. The enthusiasm was great and has kept the (cycling) transport research community on its toes to this day. As more new data sets and advanced computing techniques became available, the transport modelling community that is traditionally reliant on vast amounts

of data, was particularly optimistic to make big leaps forward [2, 3].

Currently, we see emerging data sources and data-driven applications, which bear huge potentials for the transition towards sustainable cities. With AI-driven solutions on the horizon, the topic gains additional momentum. However, this potential remains largely untapped due to slow adoption in administration and public engagement processes.

While the advancements have significantly contributed to the field, it is essential to critically reassess the impact and methodologies of data-driven cycling research.

[1] Anderson, C., The End of Theory: The Data Deluge Makes the Scientific Method Obsolete, in Wired Magazin. 2008, Condé Nast Publications: San Francisco.

[2] Miller, H.J. and S.-L. Shaw, Geographic Information Systems for Transportation in the 21st Century. Geography Compass, 2015. 9(4): p. 180-189.

[3] Anda, C., A. Erath, and P.J. Fourie, Transport modelling in the age of big data. International Journal of Urban Sciences, 2017. 21(sup1): p. 19-42.

Problem Statement

The background of the workshop is made up by the following problem statements:

- 1 There is a need to evaluate the effectiveness of data-driven approaches in promoting cycling and fostering sustainable mobility systems, especially in times of a societal and transportation policies backlash in many countries.
- 2 The concept of “data triangulation” - combining different datasets to form a comprehensive

view - needs further exploration, including methods for semantically and syntactically integrating various datasets.

- 3 Data quality issues and the identification of trustworthy datasets for ground truthing are critical when working with closed data sources. Moreover, we are concerned about the reliance on proprietary data providers and academic principles of freedom, publicness, and transparency.
- 4 The epistemological foundations of data-driven cycling research need clarification, especially in differentiating real-world phenomena from their digital representations and integrating theory-led research with big data analysis.

Workshop Setting

The workshop was part of the program of the 2025 meeting of the Cycling Research Board (#CRBAM2025). Delegates were invited to participate through an open call. 25 experts attended.

A brief introduction was followed by a World Café with three distinct guiding questions. Each table was facilitated by a permanent host: Dr. Sven Lißner (SL), Dr. Christian Werner (CW) and Dr. Martin Loidl (ML).

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IMPACT

- objectivity
- observed / objective data vs. subjective } proof (e.g. accident) => less?!
- inquiry: more data -> more possibilities
- potential causes if no/not more data => increased complexity (history) - 'coolness'
- visualization is key
- novel data -> mistrust! -> 'the old'
- communication => translating into
- how/what data -> focus on some aspect
- data has to fit context, assumptions...
- possibility to extend existing system
- consensus: accessibility to data more
- > can't-use tools -> planning sup
- NO UNIVERSAL SOLUTIONS ->
- blind spots
- Need to use appropriate (depends on question)
- avoid real action by power of interpretability & data/results: ...

Strava

≠ representative
 could be biased?
 ↳ Dep. depends on research question
 ↳ good for identifying prevailing routes & specific

Complementary value to other data + Counters
 Even Strava -> Small samples
 Differences in Data Collection Methods Bas. though non automatic collection
 MID - Distrib. level Model (MNC)
 MID ↔ SrV Data in Berlin
 Coarsened => Different results
 Level of Getting shared influences Data Quality (Birk)

Epistemology of Big Data-Driven Cycling Research

A positivistic approach to cycling data often obscures the assumptions and decisions embedded throughout the data modeling process. When we describe our environment verbally, we rely on cognitive models that linguistically represent entities and their relationships. Similarly, digital representations of cycling mobility are constructed through modeling choices.

Yet, in our research practices, how often do we critically reflect on these underlying models and their influence on our interpretations?

Participants' responses revealed that data should not be seen as a mirror of reality, but rather as an abstracted model of it. The question of what constitutes reality itself was considered beyond the scope of this session. The epistemological nature of data is closely tied to the chosen research approach - whether inductive or deductive - and its alignment with the research question. It is therefore essential to critically assess whether existing data are suitable for the research question, or to carefully design a data generation strategy when collecting new data. In either case, data represent only a snapshot of a predefined segment of reality. Often, we work with samples that inherently reflect only a portion of the whole.

Moreover, data cannot be separated from their intended purpose; they are always framed by a specific scope.

The type of data used is inherently linked to the research question and the chosen research approach. Participants differentiated between qualitative and quantitative data, as well as between subjective and objective forms. The scale and level of detail in data acquisition are shaped by the tension between complexity and the need for simplification. Emerging data source, such as tracking or mobile

phone data, are not expected to replace conventional sources. Instead, a growing number of complementary approaches is anticipated. The availability of diverse datasets enhances opportunities for triangulation and correction.

Targeted analyses based on data can address specific research questions, but the characteristics of the data determine the scope and validity of the conclusions. These conclusions, in turn, inform policy. Participants noted a significant lack of sensitivity among decision-makers regarding the dependency on data and the limitations of the conclusions that can be drawn from them.

Analyses are typically based on models of varying complexity. The validity of these models depends on the quality and characteristics of the underlying data. Additionally, assumptions introduced during modeling

influence the explanatory power of the results. Participants emphasized the need for caution when linking models to domain knowledge and deriving conclusions. Connecting these insights to policy-making requires a high degree of sensitivity. While the abundance of datasets and the diversity of available analytical methods are appreciated, the integration of these methods into mixed-methods approaches remains a topic of fundamental conceptual research.

Considerations for Various Data Sources

The use of digital cycling data was not very common among the workshop participants, but there was one data source that everyone had at least heard of: STRAVA. Datasets from the US sports app have been circulating in cycling research for more than ten years now, and everyone present was well aware of their limitations: too sporty, too male, too white. The issue of representativeness immediately became central.

For everyday cycling, Strava rides are too long, too fast, and routes may differ from those chosen in daily life. Once these disadvantages - shared, to some extent, by all self-selection-based datasets - had been quickly listed, a more reflective discussion began: What counts as representative, and for which task?

While Strava data may seem entirely unsuitable for analysing school trips, it could be highly representative when it comes to planning sport-oriented tourist routes. Representativeness, in other words, is always context-dependent.

Some contributions to the discussion went even further. Given the sheer size of the dataset, it should be possible to filter out a subset of Strava data that is representative even for everyday trips, if researchers had access to the raw data.

This, of course, touches on a central criticism that Strava

shares with many other data providers: the lack of transparency and limited accessibility.

Nevertheless, every dataset appears to hold valuable insights. The discussion made clear that the task is not so much to dismiss certain sources as unsuitable, but rather to understand what they can and cannot tell us. Even highly selective datasets may contribute useful information, provided that their limitations are acknowledged, their biases are transparent, and they are applied in the right context. One participant even admitted quite

openly that he occasionally drew inspiration from Strava data in planning processes, arguing that sports cyclists are also likely to prefer comfortable and safe routes.

Another point raised was the complementarity of different data sources, for example, GPS data and data from stationary counters - a practice already established in academia through direct demand models. Yet, the central theme of the discussion was bias and how it can be measured.

Participants noted that while self-selection is a well-known issue in GPS datasets from campaigns or supported household surveys, only fully automated data collection triggered by a participant's or their smartphone's movement can reliably eliminate another challenge, the nonresponse errors during recording. Such errors are particularly common for very short trips, both in smartphone/GPS-based collection and in household surveys.

Although household surveys are still widely considered the benchmark for cycling data, participants highlighted practical shortcomings. Based on their own experience with mobility surveys in Germany, they pointed out that even at the city level, the number of observed cycling trips is often very small. At the district level, reliable statements about cycling become nearly impossible, forcing researchers to aggregate values under the assumption of uniform behaviour across regions. This approach, however, prevents the monitoring or evaluation of local

developments.

Critical remarks were also made about household surveys as a benchmark in general, with concerns raised about comparability and transparency:

results from different official household surveys for the very same city were reported to differ significantly.

In summary, all discussed datasets come with both limitations and opportunities that the research community can and should continue to address. Initial ideas for collaboration were already discussed during the workshop.

Impact from Datafication of Cycling Research

The discussion on the impact of data-driven cycling research started with an optimistic take, focusing on its opportunities. Data may provide objective proof for assumptions or disprove them. Thus, more data being available can enable and improve research opportunities and may lead to more robust outcomes that can inform policy and planning. However, workshop participants questioned whether this actually holds true in practice.

While participants valued the potentially lower bias of objectively collected (measured) data in contrast to more subjective data input such as from surveys, they pointed out that there might be a different kind of bias. For example, selection bias and missing data (“blank spots”) can be critical. Furthermore, they discussed that each data set is created within a specific scope and with specific methods. Thus, such context needs to be properly addressed, and potentially inherent assumptions need to be considered. Especially as novel data may face skepticism and mistrust, the use of adequate input data and sound methodology is essential. A key aspect is to apply data and methods that allow for causal inference besides regarding correlations. Still, appropriate data may not be available for answering every (research) question. However, increased complexity both

in methodology and findings may pose critical barriers to create real-world impact. Thus, workshop participants identified adequate and well-targeted communication being crucial for creating impact. A key aspect is to translate results and findings into clear messages. The power of interpreting the data was seen as both a key challenge as well as a great opportunity.

Knowledge transfer and appropriate communication were regarded essential to reduce mistrust and to encourage practitioners to leave behind the established “old ways”.

Especially the use of intuitive and appealing visualizations was regarded important in communication to stakeholders.

Moving beyond classical ways of communication, the provision of easy-to-use digital tools that transfer research findings into tangible planning support applications was regarded a great facilitator for generating real-world impact. The best impact may be achieved if such tools help making life of planners easier. The availability and use of cycling data was also seen as an enabler to integrate cycling and multimodal options into existing planning support systems and models. Participants discussed that there might not be a universal solution that fits every use case and purpose. Therefore, researchers are in charge to ask the right research questions and use appropriate data and methods to create impact.

The experts also critically reflected that the lack of (suitable) input data may be utilized as potential excuse to not act. They mentioned that data collection may further be used to delay processes and to avoid real action. This is especially critical in context of restricted access to data for research purposes and the presence of data monopolies.

All in all, while the experts discussed the challenges of using cycling data and their potential limitations in reflecting reality, they also pointed out to be more confident especially in context of other stakeholders

that make use of way less-sophisticated data and methods. Depending on the respective context, this may increase impact as a result of better targeted communication.

Conclusions and Outlook

The World Café discussions underscored the complexity and potential of data-driven cycling research. Participants emphasized that data are not neutral reflections of reality but constructed representations shaped by modeling choices, research approaches, and contextual framing. The epistemological foundations of cycling data and their specific characteristics must be critically examined to ensure

alignment with research questions.

Representativeness and inherent biases (especially in self-selected and proprietary datasets) of data remain key challenges. However, the thoughtful combination of diverse data sources through triangulation and mixed-methods approaches offers promising avenues for more robust insights.

Participants also highlighted the importance of translating research into practice. Intuitive visualizations and user-friendly digital tools can bridge the gap between data analysis and planning processes, fostering real-world impact. Yet, skepticism and mistrust, especially regarding novel data, must be addressed through transparent methodologies and targeted communication. The lack of suitable data should not become an excuse for inaction.

Looking ahead, the research community must advocate for open data access, interdisciplinary collaboration, and methodological rigor. By asking the right questions and applying appropriate tools, cycling research can evolve from descriptive analysis to causal inference. Evidence generated this way serves as input for informed decision-making in increasingly complex urban environments and is a foundation for the ongoing mobility transformation.

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